

Comparative study on the damage tolerance of thermoset and thermoplastic glass fiber-reinforced composites

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BACKGROUND & MOTIVATION

Motivation

- Fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) with enhanced susceptibility to out-of-plane impact loading
- Matrix dominant material behavior

Hypothesis: Even with continuous fiber reinforcement, a **different material behavior under low-velocity impact (LVI) loading** for thermoset and thermoplastic composites is assumed, **but the same design allowables** are applied.

General objective: Generate a deep understanding of damage morphology and **damage mechanisms of thermoplastic composites** compared to thermoset FRP under out-of-plane LVI via numerical and experimental investigations.

Investigated materials

- Fiber:**
- Fiber material: **E-Glass**, 204 tex
 - Architecture: Twill weave, 2x2
 - Areal weight: 290 g/m^2
 - Finish: Silane, TF970
- Matrix:**
- Thermoset: **EP**
 - Thermoplastic: **PA66**
- Laminate:** **$[(+45/-45)/(0/90)]_{4s}$**

METHODS & RESULTS

Conditioning & impact testing

Force-time curves

Indentation measurement

Ultrasonic analyses

CONCLUSIONS & OUTLOOK

Conclusions

- Fiber fabric architecture prevents damage threshold load (DTL)
 - effect is independent from matrix material and conditioning state
- Enhanced barely visible impact damage (BVID) behavior for thermoplastic composites
 - large impactor indentation
- Temperature and water absorption of thermoplastic composites with major influence on damage tolerance
 - Absence of stored humidity is critical for moisture sensitive thermoplastic composites
 - Hot/wet specimens with small damage projection area → reduced stiffness

Outlook

- Experimental
 - Non-destructive methods: CT-Scans, cross sections
 - Correlation with humid conditioned glass fiber-reinforced thermoset specimens
 - Investigations on non-crimp fabrics
- Numerical
 - Calibration and validation of finite element simulations